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Food Security and Nutrition Framework

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Abstract

The state of food security and nutrition is a vital issue for governments. It is recommended to govern food security in a systematic approach to enable governments to achieve food security and to eliminate all forms of malnutrition. Food security and nutrition (FSN) systems should be measurable, primary food security indicators should be regularly observed and assessed. THE efficient FSN system should be capable of providing sufficient food at affordable prices for everyone. It should guarantee a stable and resilient supply to meet food demands and to deliver a nutritious and quality diet. However, the national FSN system should be capable of dealing with food security challenges and should address food security-critical and emerging issues. Achieving the desired state of food security and nutrition can be hindered by geopolitical instability and food prices and price volatility. The prevalence of poverty and hunger, especially in rural areas, would stress the food security system. Finally, sustainable agriculture and food systems are important factors for efficient food security and nutrition systems. This review paper aims to illustrate significant food security challenges that need to be considered by any food security and nutrition system

Keywords: Climate change; Geopolitical stability; Food loss and waste; Food security; Malnutrition; Poverty; Sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION

The 1996 World Food Summit reaffirmed “the right of everyone to have access to safe and nutritious food, consistent with the right to adequate food and the fundamental right of everyone to be free from hunger”. Later, in 2005, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) developed the “Voluntary Guidelines to support the progressive realization of the right to adequate food in the context of national food security”. The Voluntary Guidelines comprise 19 guidelines to be considered by governments at the national level to achieve food security while integrating human rights into the work of agencies dealing with food and agriculture (FAO, 2005).

A decade ago, the World Food Summit set-up a Millennium Development Goal #1 (MDG 1) which aimed to halve the number of hungry people around the world. Countries that could achieve the MDG 1 had accomplished economic growth and enjoyed political stability in addition to implementing social protection policies; while countries that failed to reach the MDG 1 had suffered from natural disasters and/or political instability. The percent of undernourished people was reduced from 23.3% in 1990-92 to 12.9% in 2015. The decline was more noticeable in developing countries despite the significant population growth (FAO et al., 2015b). The United Nations' Decade of Action on Nutrition 2016-2025 (part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development) aims to end hunger and all form of malnutrition by the end of 2030. The second Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 2) calls on countries to “end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture” by 2030. It suggests moving toward food security and nutrition's integrated and interrelated policy approaches and actions (FAO et al., 2017).

2. WHAT IS FOOD SECURITY

The High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE) of the FAO defines food system as “a system that embraces all the elements (environment, people, inputs, processes, infrastructure, institutions, markets and trade) and activities that relate to the production, processing, distribution and marketing, preparation and consumption of food and the outputs of these activities, including socio-economic and

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environmental outcomes” (HLPE, 2014). However, a sustainable food system is critical in resolving issues of food security, poverty alleviation, and adequate nutrition. It plays a vital role in building resilience in communities responding to a rapidly changing global environment. According to HLPE, a sustainable food system is “a food system that delivers food and nutrition security for all in such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition for future generations are not compromised” (HLPE, 2014). The International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) defines sustainable food systems as “food systems with low environmental impacts, that contribute to food and nutrition security and to healthy diets for present and future generations. Sustainable food systems are protective and respectful of biodiversity and ecosystems, as well as human well-being. They provide culturally acceptable, economically fair, affordable, nutritionally adequate, safe and healthy foods in a way that balances agro-ecosystem integrity and social welfare” (CIAT, 2018).

The 1996 World Food Summit defines food security as "the state in which all people at all times have physical, social and economic access to sufficient and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs for a healthy and active life". However, there are four dimensions of food security that need to be fulfilled to achieve food security objectives. These dimensions are physical availability of food, economic and physical access to food, food utilization, and the stability of the food security system. The first and second dimensions illustrate food availability and affordability, while the utilization and stability dimensions illustrate the resulting diet quality and the stability of food supplies (EC-FAO, 2008). Any deficiency in one or more food security dimension(s) could cause "Food Insecurity" which can be chronic (i.e. persistent or long-term), transitory (i.e. temporary or short-term), or seasonal (i.e. temporary and repeatable). Food insecurity can be defined as "a situation that exists when people lack secure access to sufficient amounts of safe and nutritious food for normal growth and development and an active and healthy life". It might be caused by insufficient food supply, inappropriate distribution, and/or inadequate purchase power (FAO et al., 2017).

Furthermore, nutrition security can be defined as "a situation that exists when secure access to an appropriately nutritious diet is coupled with a sanitary environment and adequate health services and care, to ensure a healthy and active life for all household members" (FAO et al., 2017). However, nutrition insecurity is broader than food insecurity as it considers aspects other than a sufficient diet. Nutrition insecurity can result from insufficient dietary intake, inadequate health and sanitation services/conditions, and/or inappropriate feeding and caring practices. This could lead to poor nutritional statuses such as malnutrition or undernourishment. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), undernourishment is a state of inability to acquire enough food that is sufficient to meet dietary energy requirements. Moreover, malnutrition is an abnormal physiological condition (i.e. undernutrition, overnutrition, or micronutrient deficiencies) resulted from inadequate, unbalanced, or excessive consumption of macronutrients and/or micronutrients (FAO et al., 2017).

3. FOOD SECURITY CHALLENGES

Food security and nutrition systems are facing changing critical and emerging issues. Such issues should be addressed in the FSN system. The FAO’s HLPE defines the critical issue as “an issue that has a profound influence on one or more of the dimensions of food security, either directly or indirectly, positively or negatively”, while emerging issues are “those for which there are concerns that they could become critical in the future” (HLPE, 2017). According to HLPE, there are nine critical and emerging issues related to food security and nutrition that need to be further considered. These issues include: 1) anticipating the interconnected future of urbanization and rural transformation; 2) conflicts, migrations; 3) inequalities, vulnerability, marginalized groups; 4) impacts of trade; 5) agroecology; 6) agrobiodiversity, genetic resources and modern breeding; 7) food safety and emerging diseases; 8) technology promises and knowledge; and 9) strengthening governance of food systems.

Achieving food security and nutrition is a complex multi-dimensions process. The state of food security and nutrition depends on many aspects and requires national and international cooperation to be achieved. In the food security arena, many challenges are needed to be considered by decision-makers. These challenges should be addressed in the FSN system; and actions should be in place for each challenge. However, based on an extensive review of food security and nutrition issues, there are six significant challenges facing FSN systems.

3.1 Geopolitical Instability

Geopolitical instability has a significant impact on the state of food security. Conflict and climate variability or crisis are among the key drivers of global hunger and severe food crises. Geopolitical instability undermining the four dimensions of food security (FAO et al., 2018). According to FAO, conflicts—exacerbated by climate-related shocks—significantly contribute to food insecurity. It was reported that, in 2016, more than 2 billion people were living in countries affected by conflict, violence, and/or fragility. FAO's estimates for 2016 show that 815 million people around the world are undernourished; 489 million people of which (60%) were living in countries struggling with conflict, violence, and fragility. Politically instable countries found to have a higher prevalence of undernourishment. FAO classifies 19 countries with a protracted crisis, all of them are currently affected by political instability compounded by climate shocks that severely affect agriculture and food sectors (FAO et al., 2017).

Protracted crises are long-lasting or recurring, and usually characterized by limited institutions' capacity to respond. These crises exacerbating food insecurity problem and often force people to adopt radical adjustment in their way of life. Critical responses to protracted crises include agriculture and rural economy, humanitarian food assistance, and social protection program (FAO and WFP, 2010). Prolonged political instability would cause severe food crisis (i.e. hunger, undernutrition, and/or famine), while undermining resilience capabilities. In such a case, poor people are more vulnerable to food and/or nutrition insecurity. Fragility indicates weak institutional response capacities, imminent political instability, potential prolongation of conflict, and/or probable significant adverse impacts on livelihoods. Food insecurity itself can cause fragility because it can be a trigger for violence, especially in the case of fragile institutions and pervasive inequality (FAO et al., 2017). For instance, in 2007-08, sudden spikes in food prices caused riots in more than 40 countries. Additionally, in 2017, the vast increase in food prices and a shortage in the food supply in Venezuela caused unrest and violence.

Response to food crises is vital to preserve livelihood and to promote future stability and development. It has been observed that food insecurity and undernutrition are common symptoms of protracted crises that seriously affect both livelihood and food systems. There are many underlying causes for protracted crises including man-made/natural disasters, natural resource pressures, climate change, conflict, forced migration, terrorism, inequality, inefficient governance, and/or prevalence of poverty. Nevertheless, the FAO's Committee on World Food Security (CFS) has published a framework for action in case of food security and protracted nutrition crises which comprises 11 principles addressing critical manifestations and building resilience (CFS, 2015). Resilience ability is a vital concept for coping with conflict to minimize and curtail the consequences of food and nutrition security. According to FAO, resilience is a combination of capacities including adaptive, absorptive, and transformative capacities. These capacities determine how—and to what extent—individuals, households, communities, and institutions are able to cope with and adapt to conflict's impacts (FAO et al., 2017).

On the other hand, climate change and natural resource risks are severely and disproportionately threat food security. Climate change and natural disasters are negatively affected food security by hindering crop, livestock, and fisheries production, storage, and/or distribution. Country's exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity to climate-related risks and the risks facing a country's natural assets (i.e. land, water and oceans) are critical factors that are affecting natural resources and hence food security. National governments' capacity in disaster risk management would indicate their ability to proactively addressing potential climate and resource-related concerns (EIU, 2017). Nutrition is highly susceptible to climate

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change and could affect the nutrient quality and diet diversity of food produced and consumed. This would affect health risk patterns and maternal care such as caring and feeding practices (FAO et al., 2018).

Countries should increase their agriculture sectors' resilience against climate change and natural disasters by establishing early warning systems, improving their emergency preparedness programs, and implementing appropriate agricultural policies. Additionally, unsustainable use of natural resources—caused by a lack of policies and frail management—is considered one significant risk for natural resources and food security. For instance, agriculture practices contribute to freshwater quantity and quality as the agriculture sector withdraws about 70% of freshwater (EIU, 2017). Generally, resilience is adapting coping strategies to absorb risks on assets, human, and livelihood diversification by implementing appropriate governance policies that utilize infrastructure, community networks, and formal safety nets during the crisis.

3.2 Sustainable Agriculture

In light of the 2030 Agenda on Sustainable Development and the Paris Agreement on Climate Change, achieving the goal of eliminating hunger and poverty by 2030 is more challenging. It was expected that the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture productivity and forestry would intensify in all regions beyond 2030. However, governments around the world need to take more responsible actions to build a sustainable future to reduce the vulnerability of farmers to climate shocks, and to improve rural livelihoods and food security. Sustainable agricultural practices may help to cope with the effect of climate change to improve food security. The FAO stated that "Smallholders' adaptation to climate change risks will be critical for global poverty reduction and food security" (FAO, 2016b). Usually, smallholders' adaptation to that practice is hindered by many barriers, including, but not limited to, limited access to market, credit and funding system, availability of information and tools in weather and risk management, extension advice, and social protection program. Furthermore, ensuring food security while protecting the ecosystem in the presence of resilience to climate change is a vital adaptation that is necessary to be considered in modern agriculture and food systems. However, policies that promote sustainable food and agricultural practices should be adopted as well as broad-based rural and agricultural development. Additionally, the assignment of climate financing and agricultural investments, as well as social investment, are required to enable the transition to sustainable agricultural practices, especially for smallholders (FAO, 2016b).

3.3 Rural Development

Demographic change is a vital issue in food security. Increasing population, changes in socio-economic characteristics, urbanization, and migration from rural to urban would play a critical role in food security (EIU, 2017). However, economic growth may increase income and reduce hunger if the growth is broadly shared by everyone. To utilize economic growth in reducing hunger and improving the state of food security, policies should be in-place to target rural areas where the most miserable people are expected to live. Policies that targeting agriculture productivity, smallholder support, and food availability can significantly reduce hunger, poverty, undernutrition, and/or undernourishment. Such policies if combined with social protection policies can achieve both short- and long-term food security (FAO et al., 2013). Rural development can lead to a healthy agriculture sector that can help in minimizing the effect of economic and/or food crisis. Sufficient strategic investments in the agriculture sector would reduce poverty by creating jobs; and reduce hunger by minimizing food price volatility (FAO and WFP, 2009).

Most poor people are usually in rural areas; and they are mostly relying on agriculture and related activities for their livelihoods. However, agriculture growth should target rural areas and smallholders to generate employment for the poor and to increase the return to labors. Effective and sustainable economic and agriculture growth should result in better nutritional outcomes by enhancing diets diversity especially for poor people. Growth in the agriculture sector will be useful in reducing hunger and malnutrition (FAO et al., 2012). Low agriculture productivity would increase food prices which will negatively impact food security pushing millions of low-income people to hunger (FAO, 2016b). It was perceived that, investment in agriculture and rural development would lead to economic growth and employment especially in a rural area where most of the low-income population lives (FAO et al., 2015a).

3.4 Food Trade and Price

The growing population around the world stresses global food security by increasing food demands. Increasing demand would increase food prices, hence, reduce food affordability especially for the lower-income population. Population demography could significantly affect consumption patterns and cause stress in the economy, infrastructure, and food market (EIU, 2017). In 2008, the global food price crisis and the resulted food price spikes in the global market had negatively affected millions of peoples' food security around the world especially in developing countries. Usually, in the case of the food crisis, poor people reduce their dietary diversity and reduce spending on other essential needs such as education and health care which negatively affect their quality of life and create more poverty (FAO and WFP, 2009). However, actions are needed to cope with the increasing food demand trend; and agriculture and food price volatility.

Agriculture and food trade affect the four dimensions of food security. Trade interact differently with the four food security dimensions among countries resulting in different effect in food security. Although food and agriculture trade is increasing globally, the pattern and structure of trade differ significantly among countries and commodities. Production and demand along with in-place trade policies are affecting trade and so the food security among countries. However, it is essential to continually review and evaluate current agriculture and trade policies to address weaknesses related to governance and to determine the most appropriate alternative policies (FAO, 2016a).

Agriculture and food prices volatility is one major issue related to global food security as it would increase the number of undernourished population as the price of sufficient and suitable quality meals will be unaffordable for people living around poverty line (i.e. people with income equal to 1.25 US\$ a day) (FAO et al., 2015a). Agriculture and food price volatility would be affected by geopolitical instability and energy markets. Price volatility increases the vulnerability to poverty for both poor people and smallholder farmers as it influences real income. High food prices for consumers or low food prices for farmers can lead to potential poverty traps. High food prices affect both urban and rural poor who are typically net food buyers. Nevertheless, high food prices would motivate agriculture investment, which can improve food security in the long term. Therefore, food security strategy should consider increasing agriculture productivity and facilitating agriculture and food trade (FAO et al., 2011).

3.5 Food Loss and Waste

It was estimated by FAO that one-third of all food produced is lost or wasted from farm to fork continuum. Food loss and waste express the decrease of food—that intended for human consumption—in subsequent stages of the food supply chain (FAO, 2017; UNEP and FAO, 2014). The Food Loss and Waste Protocol (FLW) estimated that each year 1 billion tons of food never gets consumed. The total lost and wasted food cost the glob around \$940 billion every year. Food loss and waste can occur in different stages along the food supply chain (FLW-Protocol, 2018). Food losses and waste are defined as “a decrease, at all stages of the food chain from harvest to consumption, in mass, of food that was originally intended for human consumption, regardless of the cause” (HLPE, 2014). According to FAO (2013), food wastage refers to "any food lost by deterioration or discard". Thus, the term “wastage” encompasses both food loss and food waste. The FAO defines food loss as "a decrease in mass (dry matter quantity) or nutritional value (quality) of food that was originally intended for human consumption". Additionally, food waste is defined as "food appropriate for human consumption being discarded, whether or not after it is kept beyond its expiry date or left to spoil. Often this is because food has spoiled but it can be for other reasons such as oversupply due to markets, or individual consumer shopping/eating habits" (FAO, 2013).

Generally, food loss is more common in developing countries, while food waste is more common in high-income developed countries. Although food waste could indicate higher food availability and greater food security, food loss would express weakened less developed food supply chains (EIU, 2014). Food losses and wastes are not a supply chain incident, they should be considered as an integral part of food systems. Food losses and waste depend on—and results of—technical, economic, and cultural functions of food systems

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(HLPE, 2014). However, a sustainable food system should control and reduce food loss and waste not only to improve the food system's efficiency but also to optimize the depletion of natural resources and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (FAO, 2016b; FAO, 2017).

In 2011, a study conducted by FAO for the International Congress illustrated that reducing food losses is a priority to balance between increasing food consumption while maintaining efficient natural resource consumption. It suggests that in low-income countries, food losses are mainly connected to "financial, managerial and technical limitations in harvesting techniques, storage and cooling facilities in difficult climatic conditions (natural disaster), infrastructure, packaging and marketing systems". However, in medium/high-income countries food loss and waste are mainly connected to lack of coordination among food supply chain firms, the sales agreements between farmers and buyers, quality standards, and consumers' behavior. Food waste in high-income countries where consumers can afford to waste food is connected to consumers' careless attitude toward food waste, insufficient purchase planning, and expiring 'best-before-dates' food. Food loss and waste in those countries may be reduced by increasing industry, retailers, and consumers' awareness regarding food loss and waste (FAO, 2011).

3.6 Poverty

Globally, in 2016, there were around 815 million chronically undernourished people, 155 million stunt children, and 52 million wasting cases in children under five years of age (FAO et al., 2017). In 2017, the number of undernourished people continued to increase reaching 821 million people around the world. Although the level of child stunting was reduced to 151 million children under five years old, the level remains unacceptable. Wasting among children affects around 50 million children under five imposing increased risk of morbidity and mortality. On the other hand, adult obesity is worsening to reach more than 672 million obese adults. The higher cost of nutritious food could cause food insecurity which contributes to malnutrition (i.e. undernutrition and obesity) as it stresses living and physiological adaptation of food insecure families. This food restriction could be one reason why food insecure families may have a higher risk of obesity and overweight. The increasing food insecurity and high level of malnutrition highlight the need for severe actions to ensure SDG 2 on food security and nutrition (FAO et al., 2018).

Governments can achieve zero-hunger by investing in social protection to protect poor people (mostly in rural areas) from food insecurity and to enhance their productivity and income. According to FAO, food expenditure ranging from 50 to 70% of the total income of the population living in the poverty line. Social protection program such as Poverty Gap Transfer (PGT) aims to bring poor people to Purchase Power Parity (PPP) to enable them to afford sufficient nutritious diet (FAO et al., 2015a). Social protection programs can significantly reduce poverty, hunger, and undernutrition in the short-term within the most vulnerable population who have not benefited from economic growth. However, to accelerate hunger reduction, economic growth should be accompanied by public policies that support pro-poor by enhancing the provision of public goods/services, ensuring equitable access to resources, and promoting human rights (FAO et al., 2012).

4. CONCLUSION

4.1 Food-system approach

The Joint Research Center of the European Commission (EC-JRC) had conducted a systematic and structured discussion approach to develop a vision for food security in 2030 to guide future EU policies. In 2015, the JRC published its report titled "Global Food Security 2030: Assessing trends with a view to guiding future EU policies". The report suggests that "by 2030 and beyond, food security will increasingly be considered as securing food supply in response to changing and growing global demand". The primary point in this report is the recommendation to look systematically at food security and its inherited complex nature and to move from food-security to food-system approach which incorporates systematic and global dimensions of food security. The JRC foresees that food security can be guaranteed by significant transformation of agriculture system, rural development, balancing food production and consumption, and

considering consumers' behavior (i.e. demand-driven food system). These interventions are focusing on smallholder farmers helping them to transform into competitive agribusinesses to ensure food security, reduce poverty, and to ensure sustainable use of natural resources. Facilitating such transformation requires providing smallholders (or generally rural areas) with suitable infrastructure, information systems, nutrition programs, risk management tools, and coordination between public and private stakeholders. However, to achieve food security its required to maintain a food system based on a framework of policies that addressing innovation, commerce, and trade in the various aspects of global food chains (EC-JRC, 2015).

4.2 National FSN Framework

Although the major objective of any FSN system is to fight hunger, the FSN system should also be capable of meeting food demand. It is fundamental that a comprehensive understanding of the FSN system would facilitate future planning, development, and decision-making. Achieving food security requires governments to follow an integrated approach. Food security and nutrition should be managed and governed by an inclusive and systematic framework (Fig. 2). Governance of food security should be central to the national legal framework. The national food security and nutrition framework should be addressed by national laws and regulations. FSN systems should have several corelated, coordinated, and integrated components to enable countries to achieve the desired state of food security and nutrition.

Figure 2. National FSN System Framework

(●) Indicates FSN system's component

National FSN system should comprise at least the following components:

- 1- Food and agriculture legal framework that addressing FSN's framework, food security dimensions, and critical and emerging issues.
- 2- Sustainable agriculture and food systems that efficiently meet food and nutrition demands without deploying natural resources, and with the capability to adapt to a changing environment and food market.
- 3- The rural development program that supports rural population, enabling smallholders, and promote sustainable agriculture.
- 4- Social protection programs that are efficient in eliminating all forms of poverty and hunger.
- 5- National nutrition program that is capable of assessing the national state of food insecurity and nutrition (i.e. food utilization dimension). It should enable the neediest people to get a nutritious diet (e.g. Safety Net) and eliminate malnutrition.
- 6- Resilience and emergency preparedness plans that are capable of saving people, especially poor ones, in case of geopolitical instability and food crises.

4.3 Assessment of food security dimensions

As food security is a complex condition, it is better to present its four dimensions as a suite of indicators to better understand and evaluate the food security state (FAO et al., 2013). Therefore, the national authority responsible for food security should operate in a systematic approach to achieve food security. They should apply the best measures to observe and assess the current state of food security nationally, regionally, and internationally. The four dimensions of food security should be regularly measured and observed; and the food security decision-making process should be based on reliable and up-to-date food security indicators (Alshuniaber, 2019).

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